

Resilient Technologies – Workshop Documents

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Abstract

Single-source `.dtx` for the *Resilient Technologies* workshop. Extracts the shared preamble, the full instructor guide, and the participant handout via `latex resilient-technologies.ins`.

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Introduction

This file is the single source for all workshop documents belonging to the *Resilient Technologies* workshop on reproducible Research Data Management. It follows the `docstrip` convention: documentation and code live together in one `.dtx` file; running `latex resilient-technologies.ins` extracts the individual output files.

Motivation

Keeping a single source ensures that every output – the instructor guide, the participant handout, the quick reference card, and the executable org-mode demo file – stays in sync. A change to a code block, a challenge, or a flag description is made once and propagates to all documents on the next extraction and compilation run.

How to build

1. Extract all output files from the `.dtx`: `latex resilient-technologies.ins`
2. Compile the instructor guide (requires `-shell-escape` for `minted`): `lualatex -shell-escape resilient-technologies-guide.tex`

3. Compile the participant handout: `lualatex -shell-escape resilient-technologies-handout.tex`
4. Compile this documentation: `lualatex resilient-technologies.dtx`
5. The org-mode demo file is extracted to `workshop-documents/nfdi-analysis.org` without a docstrip preamble; execute it in Emacs with `C-c C-v t` to tangle all source blocks, then run `make` in `workshop-documents/` to evaluate and export.

All steps are automated via the top-level makefile: `make` extracts, compiles all \LaTeX documents, and runs the org-mode pipeline in one invocation.

File structure

Guard overview

Guards control which lines docstrip copies into which output file. The `|` operator is OR: a line tagged `<guide|handout>` appears in *both* the guide and the handout. The table below lists every guard used in this file.

- <preamble>** The complete shared \LaTeX preamble: packages, colours, fonts, all box environments, section styling, header/footer, and the `\restTitlepage` command. Extracted to `resilient-technologies-preamble.sty`, which every other \LaTeX output loads via `\usepackage`.
- <guide>** Instructor-only content: full demo prose, instructor tips, key-point boxes, flag tables, and the session plan. Loads the preamble with option `guide`. Extracted to `resilient-technologies-guide.tex`.
- <handout>** Participant handout containing only the challenge boxes and section headings, with no instructor notes or demo code. Loads the preamble with option `handout`. Extracted to `resilient-technologies-handout.tex`.
- <reference>** Quick reference card listing all demo commands in compact form. Extracted to `resilient-technologies-reference.tex` and included into both the guide and the handout via `\input`.
- <org>** The executable org-mode demo file. Extracted *without* a docstrip preamble or postamble (see `\nopreamble/ \nopostamble` in the `.ins` file) so the result is a clean, valid `.org` file that Emacs can open directly. Extracted to `workshop-documents/nfdi-analysis.org`.
- <guide|handout>** Challenge boxes with their numbered title, enumerate steps, optional `\hint`, and optional `\bonus`. Written verbatim to both the guide and the handout.
- <guide|reference>** The `clibox` opening and closing lines that wrap each demo block in the guide and the reference card. The actual source block content sits inside a narrower `<guide|reference|org>` guard so that the org file receives the raw code without the \LaTeX wrapper.
- <guide|reference|org>** The raw org-babel source block content (name, header arguments, code). Written to the guide (inside a `clibox`), the reference card (also inside a `clibox`), and the org demo file (as plain text).
- <guide|org>** Content that belongs in the guide and the org file but not the reference card – for example the org metadata header (`\#+TITLE:`, `\#+AUTHOR:`, etc.).

Package options

Both the guide and the handout load `resilient-technologies-preamble` with a single option that selects the appropriate layout variant.

- guide** Blue filled `\colorbox` section headers; dot-leader subsection lines; running head “Instructor Guide”; TOC depth 2.
- handout** Simple blue colour and rule for sections; running head “Participant Handout”; no TOC.

When the preamble is loaded by the `.dtx` driver itself (to typeset this documentation), neither option is passed and `\restType` falls back to the `\providecommand` default `Documentation`.

Version and date

Version and date are defined once in the `<internal|preamble>` guard at the top of the file:

```
% %<*internal|preamble>
```

```
% \def\restVersion{1.0.0}
% \def\restDate{2026-03-22}
% %</internal|preamble>
%
```

The `internal` guard makes them available to the `ltxdoc` driver (so `\date` can reference `\restDate`); the `preamble` guard copies them into the extracted `.sty`. Bumping the version requires editing exactly one place.

Package options

guide Blue filled section headers; running head “Instructor Guide”; TOC depth 2.

handout Simple blue section rule; running head “Participant Handout”; no TOC.

Documents

Shared preamble (the complete `.sty`)

```
1 (*preamble)
2 \NeedsTeXFormat{LaTeX2e}
3 \ProvidesPackage{resilient-technologies-preamble}
4   [\restDate\ v\restVersion\ Resilient Technologies shared preamble]
5
6 % -- Package options -----
7 \newif\if@restguide
8 \newif\if@resthandout
9 \DeclareOption{guide}  {\@restguidetrue}
10 \DeclareOption{handout}{\@resthandouttrue}
11 \ProcessOptions\relax
12
13 \def\restDOI{10.5281/zenodo.19131603}
14 \newcommand\restVersionText{version \texttt{\restVersion}}
15 \newcommand\restDOIlink{\href{https://doi.org/\restDOI}{\texttt{\restDOI}}}
16
17 \providecommand\InfoTeX{LuaLaTeX}
18 \providecommand\InfoEmacs{}
19 \providecommand\InfoOrg{}
20 \providecommand\restType{Documentation}
21
22 \if@restguide
23   \def\restType{Instructor Guide}
24 \fi
25 \if@resthandout
26   \def\restType{Participant Handout}
27 \fi
28
29 % -- Encoding & Language -----
30 \usepackage[main=english]{babel}
31 \usepackage{fontspec}
32 \setmainfont[
33   Numbers      = {Monospaced, OldStyle},
34   Scale        = 0.95,
35   ItalicFont   = Roboto-LightItalic,
36   BoldFont     = Roboto-Medium,
37 ]{Roboto-Light}
38 \setmonofont[Scale=0.88]{JetBrains Mono}
39
40 % -- Layout -----
41 \usepackage[
```

```

42  a4paper,
43  top    = 2.2cm,
44  bottom = 2.5cm,
45  left   = 2.2cm,
46  right  = 2.2cm,
47  headheight = 14pt,
48 ]{geometry}
49 \usepackage{microtype}
50 \setlength{\parindent}{0pt}
51 \setlength{\parskip}{5pt}
52
53 % -- Colors -----
54 \usepackage[RGB,table]{xcolor}
55 \definecolor{rwth-blue}{RGB}{ 0, 84, 159}
56 \definecolor{rwth-blue-50}{RGB}{142, 186, 229}
57 \definecolor{rwth-blue-25}{RGB}{199, 221, 242}
58 \definecolor{rwth-blue-10}{RGB}{232, 241, 250}
59 \definecolor{accent-orange}{RGB}{212, 101, 0}
60 \definecolor{accent-green}{RGB}{ 39, 107, 59}
61 \definecolor{accent-green-bg}{RGB}{234, 244, 238}
62 \definecolor{code-bg}{RGB}{238, 242, 247}
63 \definecolor{hint-gold}{RGB}{180, 134, 11}
64
65 % -- Graphics & Icons -----
66 \usepackage{graphicx}
67 \graphicspath{{img/}}
68 \usepackage{ccicons}
69 \usepackage{dingbat}
70 \usepackage{pifont}
71
72 \newcommand{\icontarget}{\textbf{\ding{228}}}
73 \newcommand{\icontip}{\textbf{\ding{45}}}
74 \newcommand{\iconchallenge}{\textbf{\ding{42}}}
75 \newcommand{\iconbonus}{\textbf{\ding{72}}}
76
77 \setcounter{tocdepth}{2}
78
79 % -- tcolorbox + minted -----
80 \usepackage[minted, most, skins, breakable]{tcolorbox}
81 \tcbset{
82   listing engine = minted,
83   minted options = {
84     fontsize      = \small,
85     baselinestretch = .85,
86     breaklines,
87     breakanywhere,
88     autogobble,
89     style         = friendly,
90   },
91 }
92 \renewcommand{\mintinline}[3][\texttt{\detokenize{#3}}]
93
94 % -- Box styles -----
95
96 % myhbox tcbstyle
97 \makeatletter
98 \tcbset{myhbox/.style 2 args={%
99   enhanced, breakable,
100   colback = white,
101   colframe = rwth-blue,
102   attach boxed title to top left = {yshift*=-\tcbboxedtitleheight},
103   title = {#2},
104   boxed title size = title,
105   boxed title style = {

```

```

106     sharp corners, rounded corners=northwest,
107     colback = tcbcolframe,
108     boxrule = 0pt,
109 },
110 underlay boxed title = {
111     \path[fill=tcbcolframe]
112         (title.south west)--(title.south east)
113         to[out=0, in=180] ([xshift=5mm]title.east)--
114         (title.center-|frame.east)
115         [rounded corners=\kvtcb@arc] |- (frame.north) -| cycle;
116 },
117 #1,
118 }}
119 \makeatother
120
121 % Code listing box
122 \newtcblisting{clibox}[2][]{%
123     myhbox = {fonttitle=\ttfamily\small\bfseries, coltitle=rwth-blue}{#2},
124     breakable, enhanced jigsaw, listing only,
125     minted language = #1,
126     boxrule = 0.4pt,
127     colframe = rwth-blue-25,
128     colback = code-bg,
129     opacityback = 0.5,
130     left = 4pt, right = 4pt, top = 3pt, bottom = 3pt}
131
132 % Inline code box
133 \newtcblisting{inlinecode}[1][bash]{%
134     listing only, breakable, enhanced jigsaw,
135     minted language = #1,
136     colframe = rwth-blue-25, colback = code-bg, opacityback = 0.5,
137     boxrule = 0.3pt,
138     left = 8pt, right = 4pt, top = 2pt, bottom = 2pt,
139     sharp corners,
140     borderline west = {3pt}{0pt}{rwth-blue}}
141
142 % Key-points box
143 \newtcolorbox{keypointsbox}{%
144     enhanced, breakable,
145     colback = rwth-blue-10,
146     colframe = rwth-blue,
147     boxrule = 0.6pt,
148     left = 8pt, right = 8pt, top = 6pt, bottom = 6pt,
149     fonttitle = \bfseries\small,
150     title = {\icontarget\enspace Key Points to Convey},
151     coltitle = rwth-blue,
152     attach boxed title to top left = {yshift=-2mm, xshift=4mm},
153     boxed title style = {
154         colback = rwth-blue-10,
155         colframe = rwth-blue,
156         boxrule = 0.6pt}}
157
158 % Instructor tips box
159 \newtcolorbox{tipsbox}{%
160     enhanced, breakable,
161     colback = {orange!6},
162     colframe = accent-orange,
163     boxrule = 0.6pt,
164     left = 8pt, right = 8pt, top = 6pt, bottom = 6pt,
165     borderline west = {3pt}{0pt}{accent-orange},
166     fonttitle = \bfseries\small,
167     title = {\icontip\enspace Instructor Tips},
168     coltitle = accent-orange,
169     attach boxed title to top left = {yshift=-2mm, xshift=4mm},

```

```

170 boxed title style = {
171     colback = orange!6,
172     colframe = accent-orange,
173     boxrule = 0.6pt}}
174
175 % Challenge box (auto-numbered)
176 \newcolorbox[auto counter]{challengebox}[1]{%
177     enhanced, breakable,
178     colback = accent-green-bg,
179     colframe = accent-green,
180     boxrule = 0.6pt,
181     left = 8pt, right = 8pt, top = 6pt, bottom = 6pt,
182     borderline west = {3pt}{0pt}{accent-green},
183     fonttitle = \bfseries\small,
184     title = {\iconchallenge\enspace Challenge~\thetcbcounter: #1\quad
185             {\normalfont\itshape(\approx 5 min)}},
186     coltitle = accent-green,
187     attach boxed title to top left = {yshift=-2mm, xshift=4mm},
188     boxed title style = {
189         colback = accent-green-bg,
190         colframe = accent-green,
191         boxrule = 0.6pt}}
192
193 % Hint / Bonus
194 \newcommand{\hint}{\medskip\noindent
195     \textcolor{accent-green}{\textbf{Hint:}}\par\nopagebreak}
196 \newcommand{\bonus}[1]{%
197     \smallskip\noindent
198     \textcolor{hint-gold}{\textbf{\iconbonus\enspace Bonus:\enspace}}%
199     {\small\itshape #1}\par}
200
201 % Break card
202 \newcolorbox{breakcard}{%
203     enhanced,
204     colback = accent-orange,
205     colframe = accent-orange,
206     sharp corners,
207     left = 0pt, right = 0pt, top = 8pt, bottom = 8pt,
208     halign = center}
209
210 % -- Lists -----
211 \usepackage{enumitem}
212 \setlist[itemize] {leftmargin=1em, itemsep=1pt, topsep=3pt, parsep=0pt}
213 \setlist[enumerate] {leftmargin=1.6em, itemsep=2pt, topsep=3pt, parsep=0pt}
214 \setlist[description]{font=\ttfamily\bfseries,
215     labelwidth=1.5cm,
216     leftmargin=1.6em, itemsep=2pt, topsep=3pt, parsep=0pt}
217
218 % -- Section styling -----
219 \usepackage{titlesec}
220
221 \newcommand{\sectionbox}[1]{%
222     \colorbox{rwth-blue}{%
223         \parbox{\dimexpr\linewidth-2\fbboxsep}{%
224             \strut\normalfont\Large\bfseries\color{white}#1\strut}}}
225 \newcommand{\subsectionline}[1]{%
226     #1\hspace{4pt}\leaders\hbox{\textcolor{rwth-blue-25}{.}}\hfill\mbox{}}
227 \newcommand{\tcbheading}[1]{\begin{sectitlebox}{#1}\end{sectitlebox}}
228 \newcolorbox{sectitlebox}[1]{myhbox={frame empty}{#1}, nobeforeafter,
229     after=\vspace*{-1.75\baselineskip}}
230
231 \titleformat{\section}{\ttfamily\Large\bfseries}{}{0pt}{\tcbheading}
232 \titlespacing{\section}{0pt}{14pt}{6pt}
233

```

```

234 \titleformat{\subsection}
235   {\normalfont\large\bfseries\color{rwth-blue}}{}{0pt}{\subsectionline}
236 \titlespacing{\subsection}{0pt}{10pt}{4pt}
237
238 \titleformat{\subsubsection}
239   {\normalfont\normalsize\bfseries\color{rwth-blue!80}}{}{0pt}{}
240 \titlespacing{\subsubsection}{0pt}{7pt}{2pt}
241
242 \titleformat{\paragraph}[runin]{\normalfont\normalsize\bfseries}{}{0pt}{}
243 \titleformat{\subparagraph}[runin]{\normalfont\normalsize\itshape}{}{0pt}{}
244
245 % -- Header / Footer -----
246 \usepackage{scrlayer-scrpage}
247 \pagestyle{scrheadings}
248 \clearpairofpagestyles
249 \ohead{\textcolor{rwth-blue!60}{\small
250   Resilient Technologies --- \restType} --- \restVersionText}
251 \ofoot{\textcolor{rwth-blue!60}{\small\thepage}}
252 \ifoot{\textcolor{rwth-blue!40}{\tiny\itshape RWTH Aachen University · IT Center}}
253
254 % -- Hyperlinks -----
255 \usepackage{hyperref}
256 \hypersetup{colorlinks=true, urlcolor=rwth-blue, linkcolor=rwth-blue}
257
258 % -- Misc helpers -----
259 \usepackage{array, booktabs, tabularray, multicol}
260 \newcommand{\rdmphase}[1]{\textcolor{rwth-blue!70}{\small\itshape #1}}
261 \newcommand{\toolyear}[2]{\textbf{#1}\enspace\textcolor{accent-orange}{\small(#2)}}
262
263 % -- Title page -----
264 \newcommand{\restTitlepage}{%
265   \begin{titlepage}
266     \color{rwth-blue}
267     \vspace*{1cm}
268     \begin{center}
269       {\large\bfseries\color{accent-orange}
270         \textsc{\restType} (\restVersion)}\|[1.2em]
271       \includegraphics[width=\linewidth]{resilient-technologies-header}\|
272       {\normalsize Workshop Duration: {3 hours}\quad\quad
273         Format: Hands-on with live demos}\|[0.5em]
274       {\small Lukas C. Bossert\quad\quad
275         IT Center, RWTH Aachen University}\|[0.3em]
276       {\small\href{mailto:bossert@itc.rwth-aachen.de}%
277         {bossert@itc.rwth-aachen.de}}\|[1cm]
278       \includegraphics[width=5cm]{logo-root}
279     \end{center}
280     \vfill
281     {\noindent
282       \includegraphics[height=1.2cm]{powered_by_emacs}\space
283       \includegraphics[height=1.2cm]{powered_by_org_mode}\quad
284       \begin{minipage}[b]{5cm}\tiny
285         \InfoTeX\|
286         Emacs: \InfoEmacs\|
287         Org-mode: \InfoOrg\|
288         \ccbysa\quad DOI: \restDOIlink\hfill
289       \end{minipage}
290     \par\noindent
291     \includegraphics[height=1cm]{logo-dkz2r-long}%
292     \includegraphics[height=.75cm]{BMFTR}%
293     \includegraphics[height=.5cm]{Förderhinweis-EU_horizontal}%
294     \hfill
295     \includegraphics[height=1cm]{logo-rpdm}\quad
296     \includegraphics[height=1cm]{logo-rwth-itc}}
297   \end{titlepage}}

```

298 </preamble>

Single Source Document

```

299 (*guide | handout)
300 \documentclass[a4paper,11pt]{scrartcl}
301 \usepackage[
302 (guide)guide
303 (handout)handout
304 ]{resilient-technologies-preamble}
305 \begin{document}
306 \restTitlepage
307 </guide | handout>
308 (*guide)
309 \tableofcontents
310
311 % -- Workshop Overview -----
312 \section{Workshop Overview}
313
314 \textbf{Concept:} This workshop demonstrates how decades-old yet robust
315 command-line tools can be combined into a literate programming workflow for
316 Research Data Management (RDM). All demos use a single running use case:
317 analysing the \textbf{NFDI Consortia Collaboration Dataset} from Zenodo.
318
319 \medskip
320 \textbf{Use Case Dataset:}
321 \mintinline{text}{Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv} ---
322 downloaded live from Zenodo (DOI:
323 \href{https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15880071}{10.5281/zenodo.15880071}).
324
325 \medskip
326 \textbf{Narrative thread:}\quad
327 download $\rightarrow$ clean $\rightarrow$ validate $\rightarrow$
328 analyse $\rightarrow$ automate $\rightarrow$ archive
329
330 \subsection{3-Hour Session Plan}
331 \begin{tblr}{
332   width = \linewidth,
333   colspec = {Q[wd=1.8cm, font=\bfseries\small, fg=rwth-blue-50]
334             X[font=\bfseries\small, fg=rwth-blue]
335             Q[wd=7cm, font=\itshape\small]},
336   row{1} = {bg=rwth-blue, fg=white, font=\bfseries\small},
337   row{3,5,7,9,11} = {bg=rwth-blue-25},
338 }
339   Time & Topic & Notes \\
340   10 min & Welcome \& Context & Slides + poster overview \\
341   20 min & Emacs / org-mode (1976/2003) & Metadata, markup, org-babel, tables \\
342   15 min & curl (1997) & Download + checksum comparison \\
343   15 min & sed (1974) & In-place fix with backup \\
344   10 min & grep (1973) & Verify cleaning, complex pattern \\
345   10 min & diff (1974) & Compare original and cleaned CSV \\
346   10 min & \ding{108} Break & \\
347   30 min & make (1976) & Makefile, \texttt{EMACS\_FLAGS}, DRY principle \\
348   40 min & awk (1977) & Inline, awk block, \texttt{:var}, \texttt{:dir}/\texttt{:fil
349   10 min & tar (1979) & Archive + checksum \\
350   10 min & Wrap-up: ROOT concept & Discussion + Q\&A \\
351 \end{tblr}
352
353
354 \subsection{Before You Start --- Setup Checklist}
355 \begin{itemize}
356 \item Emacs + org-mode available (or a terminal + text editor for fallback)
357 \item Poster PDF displayed on a secondary screen or printed for reference
358 \item Zenodo API accessible for the curl checksum demo
359 \end{itemize}

```

```

360
361 \begin{tipsbox}
362 \begin{itemize}
363   \item The entire workshop follows a single narrative arc: one dataset, one
364     pipeline, many tools. Always refer back to this thread.
365   \item Each tool section is self-contained --- skip \texttt{awk} or \texttt{tar}
366     without breaking earlier sections if time is short.
367   \item Encourage participants to type along. Mistakes are teaching moments.
368   \item Emphasise ROOT throughout: \textbf{R}obust, \textbf{O}pen,
369     \textbf{O}ngoing, \textbf{T}ime-tested.
370 \end{itemize}
371 \end{tipsbox}
372
373 \clearpage
374 % -- Introduction -----
375 \section{Introduction & Context --- 10 min}
376
377 Open with the \textbf{Resilient Technologies} poster. Walk participants through
378 the data-driven visualisation circle.
379
380 \subsubsection{Talking Points}
381 \begin{itemize}
382   \item Modern RDM relies on ever-growing platform landscapes --- short life cycles,
383     proprietary lock-in, and limited sustainability are real risks.
384   \item Tools like Emacs, sed, awk, curl, and tar have been around for 25--50 years.
385     They persist because of clarity, openness, and active communities.
386   \item Today's session shows how to combine these tools in a single, reproducible
387     pipeline --- using one real dataset as the connecting thread.
388   \item \textbf{ROOT badge:} Robust, Open, Ongoing, Time-tested --- introduce now,
389     return at the end.
390 \end{itemize}
391
392 \begin{keypointsbox}
393 \begin{itemize}
394   \item These tools are not relics --- they are the quiet backbone of HPC clusters,
395     data archives, and scientific workflows worldwide.
396   \item Plain-text formats (CSV, org, Makefile) are inherently FAIR: findable,
397     accessible, interoperable, reusable.
398   \item The goal is not to replace Python/R --- it is to show what you can do
399     \emph{before} you even open a script.
400 \end{itemize}
401 \end{keypointsbox}
402
403 % -- Emacs / org-mode -----
404 \section{Emacs / org-mode (1976 / 2003) --- 20 min}
405
406 \rdmphase{Planning · Production · Analysis · Archiving · Access · Re-use}
407
408 \medskip
409 Emacs is not just a text editor --- it is a fully extensible research environment.
410 \textbf{org-mode} turns plain text into a semantic markup language, task manager,
411 analysis script, and publication tool simultaneously.
412
413 \subsubsection{Core Message}
414 \textbf{Emacs + org-mode} = a single, versionable, plain-text medium that unifies
415 the entire research workflow. This very poster was written, executed, and typeset
416 from one \texttt{.org} file.
417
418 \subsection{Demo 1 --- File Metadata / Self-Describing Document}
419
420 Create a new \texttt{.org} file (\texttt{nfdi-meta-analysis.org} with
421 \verb|C-x C-f|) and fill it first with some metadata.
422 Below you find an example set of metadata.
423 Explain each keyword:

```

```

424
425 \begin{clibox}[org]{org-mode metadata}
426 </guide>
427 <*guide | org>
428 #+TITLE: NFDI Analysis
429 #+SUBTITLE: Collaborations of NFDI Consortia 2025
430 #+AUTHOR: Lukas C. Bossert
431 #+DATE: [2026-03-24]
432 #+EMAIL: bossert@itc.rwth-aachen.de
433 #+LANGUAGE: en
434 #+FILETAGS: nfdi:coding:reproducibility
435 </guide | org>
436 <*guide>
437 \end{clibox}
438
439 \begin{itemize}
440 \item These keywords drive exports (PDF/HTML/Markdown), search, and project automation.
441 \item Because they live in plain text, they travel with the file --- FAIR-friendly
442 context without external databases.
443 \end{itemize}
444
445 \subsection{Demo 2 --- Semantic Markup}
446 You can continue and show some of the markup possibilities in an org-mode file.
447
448 \begin{clibox}[org]{org-mode's semantic markup}
449 *bold* /italics/ underline +strike-through+ ~code~ footnote:[fn]
450 [[https://orgmode.org][Org website]] =verbatim= [cite:@<bibtexkey>]
451 [[file.pdf][PDF]]
452 \end{clibox}
453
454 \begin{itemize}
455 \item Org's syntax is standardised and extensible; links have types (web, file, ID),
456 citations integrate natively.
457 \item The same source renders into PDF, HTML, Markdown --- without rewriting.
458 \end{itemize}
459
460 \subsection{Demo 3 --- org-babel: Literate Programming}
461 This is the key part of the workshop. Make sure you introduce it properly.
462
463 Show a live code block; execute it with \texttt{C-c C-c}.
464 Below you find an example use. Adjust it to your needs.
465 </guide>
466 <*guide | reference>
467 \begin{clibox}[org]{org-babel code block}
468 </guide | reference>
469 <org>
470 <org>* Introduction to Literate Programming
471 <*guide | reference | org>
472 #+name: the folder structure of HOME
473 #+begin_src bash :eval yes :results verbatim
474 ls ~ | head -2
475 #+end_src
476 </guide | reference | org>
477 <org>
478 <*guide | reference>
479 \end{clibox}
480 </guide | reference>
481 <*guide>
482
483 \begin{itemize}
484 \item Code, parameters, outputs, and narrative live together in one file.
485 \item Results are cached; the entire pipeline can be re-run at any time.
486 \item Version-controlled  $\$$ \to $\$$  auditable trail from raw data to conclusions.
487 \end{itemize}

```

```

488
489 \begin{tipsbox}
490 You can point out that instead of writing arguments to the source block one can create a general defin
491 \begin{clibox}[org]{Header commands}
492 #+PROPERTY: header-args          :mkdirp yes   :results verbatim
493 #+PROPERTY: header-args:bash     :results verbatim
494 \end{clibox}
495 \end{tipsbox}
496
497 \subsection{[Optional] Demo 4 --- Org Tables with Formulas}
498 If there is time and demand, you can introduce org-mode as a way to write
499 spreadsheets.
500 </guide>
501 <*guide | reference>
502 \begin{clibox}[org]{org-mode for spreadsheets}
503 </guide | reference>
504 <org>* org-mode as spreadsheet manager
505 <*guide | reference | org>
506 #+name: Overview of consortia and research areas
507 | domain          | consortia | datasets | avg |   % |
508 |-----+-----+-----+-----+-----|
509 | Life Sciences   |          8 |       123 |  15 | 13.6 |
510 | Humanities      |          6 |       150 |  25 | 16.6 |
511 | Engineering Sc. |          5 |       173 |  35 | 19.1 |
512 | Natural Sciences |          7 |       458 |  65 | 50.7 |
513 |-----+-----+-----+-----+-----|
514 | TOTAL           |         26 |       904 |    |    |
515 #+TBLFM: @>$2=vsum(@2$2..@-1$2);%.0f::@>$3=vsum(@2$3..@-1$3);%.0f
516 #+TBLFM: @2$4..@-1$4=$3/$2;%.0f::@2$5..@-1$5=100*$3/@>$3;%.1f
517 </guide | reference | org>
518 <org>
519 <*guide | reference>
520 \end{clibox}
521 </guide | reference>
522 <*guide>
523
524
525 \begin{itemize}
526   \item Tables are plain text, diff-friendly, and export to CSV/\LaTeX{/HTML.
527   \item Recalculation is transparent --- no hidden spreadsheets or manual copy-paste.
528 \end{itemize}
529
530 \begin{tipsbox}
531 \begin{itemize}
532   \item If participants don't have Emacs, show everything from the poster PDF
533         side-by-side. The concepts transfer to any plain-text workflow.
534   \item The Trajan font anecdote is a good ice-breaker: even typography choices
535         can carry the ``resilience'' metaphor.
536   \item org-babel is the conceptual bridge to the rest of the workshop ---
537         everything that follows can live inside a \texttt{.org} file.
538         (\texttt{makefile} is an exception)
539 \end{itemize}
540 \end{tipsbox}
541 </guide>
542 <handout>\section{Challenges}
543 <*guide | handout>
544 \begin{challengebox}{Your Second Literate Document}
545 \begin{enumerate}
546   \item Create a new file \texttt{my-meta-analysis.org} in your current working directory.
547   \item Add \verb|#+TITLE:|, \verb|#+AUTHOR:|, and \verb|#+DATE:| metadata at the top.
548   \item Write a heading \texttt{* Data Overview} and a short sentence below it.
549   \item Insert an org-babel code block that runs \texttt{wc nfdi-analysis.org}.
550   \item Execute the block with \texttt{C-c C-c} and confirm the result appears
551         as \verb|#+RESULTS:|.

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552 \end{enumerate}
553 \bonus{What happens when you apply a name (\texttt{\#+name: my-source}) to the
554   org-babel source block? What is the benefit?}
555 \end{challengebox}
556 </guide | handout>
557 <*guide>
558 % -- curl -----
559 \section{curl (1997) --- 15 min}
560 \rdmphase{Planning · Access · Re-use}
561
562 \medskip
563 \texttt{curl} is the standard tool for scriptable, reproducible data transfer.
564 Unlike browser downloads, \texttt{curl} can be parameterised, logged, and audited ---
565 core requirements of Good Scientific Practice.
566
567 \subsubsection{RDM Context}
568 \begin{itemize}
569   \item Access files and metadata from repositories (Zenodo, Dataverse).
570   \item Automate REST API queries for research data and publications.
571   \item Validate file integrity through checksum comparison.
572   \item Script reproducible data acquisition processes.
573 \end{itemize}
574
575 \begin{clibox}[org]{basic syntax}
576 \#+begin_src bash :eval never
577 curl [FLAGS] [URL]
578 \#+end_src
579 \end{clibox}
580
581
582 \subsection{Demo 1 --- Download the File}
583
584 </guide>
585 <*guide | reference>
586 \begin{clibox}[org]{download with progress and resume}
587 </guide | reference>
588 <org>* curl (1997)
589 <org>** Retrieve file from Zenodo
590 <*guide | reference | org>
591 \#+name: retrieve-source-file
592 \#+begin_src bash
593 curl -L -O -# "https://zenodo.org/records/15880071/files/Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv" && echo
594 \#+end_src
595 </guide | reference | org>
596 <org>
597 <*guide | reference>
598 \end{clibox}
599 </guide | reference>
600 <*guide>
601
602 \begin{description}
603   \item[-O] Save with the server's filename.
604   \item[-C -] Resume an interrupted download; won't overwrite existing file.
605   \item[-\#] Show a progress bar instead of the default meter.
606 \end{description}
607
608 Take a look at the file and discuss what you can see.
609 Here's a summary of the file:
610
611 \textbf{What it is:} A semicolon-delimited CSV cataloguing collaborations between
612 NFDI consortia (Germany's National Research Data Infrastructure).
613 Each row documents a specific collaborative activity.
614
615 \textbf{Structure --- six columns:} Type, Name, Affiliation Lead/Chair, Participating

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616 Consortia, Frequency, Output, and Status.
617 Types of collaborations visible in the data include:
618 Alliances --- formal partnerships like Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs) between
619 consortia, joint use cases, and working groups.
620
621 \textbf{Event: conference organisation}: jointly organized workshops, symposia, and
622 conferences (e.g., the NFDI Berlin-Brandenburg network meetings, deRSE sessions).
623
624 \textbf{Event: conference participation}: shared booths, joint posters, panel
625 discussions at external conferences (DHd, E-Science-Tage, Love Data Week, RDA
626 plenaries, etc.).
627
628 The file covers a wide time range, roughly 2021--2025, with many activities in
629 2024--2025. Statuses include completed, ongoing, and future.
630 Dozens of NFDI consortia appear (NFDI4Chem, FAIRmat, MaRDI, DataPLANT, Text+,
631 GHGA, NFDI4Health, NFDI4BIOIMAGE, PUNCH4NFDI, NFDI4DataScience, NFDIxCS, and
632 many more), showing extensive cross-domain networking.
633
634 There's a \textbf{data quality issue} you will be fixing now in the following
635 steps --- some entries have the typo ``NFDI-NFDI-MatWerk'' instead of
636 ``NFDI-MatWerk.''
637
638 \subsection{Demo 2 --- Get File Checksums}
639 When comparing checksums of files you can make sure that the file has not been
640 corrupted during download. That is why we compare the remote's file checksum
641 with the local one we have downloaded before.
642
643 First you show how to retrieve the checksum of the remote file.
644 For later we need this block being named.
645 </guide>
646 <*guide | reference>
647 \begin{clibox}[org]{query Zenodo API}
648 </guide | reference>
649 <org>** Get the checksum from remote file
650 <*guide | reference | org>
651 #+name: curl-checksum
652 #+begin_src bash
653 curl -sL "https://zenodo.org/api/records/15880071" |
654 jq -r '.files[] | select(.key=="Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv") | .checksum' | awk -F: '{print $2}'
655 #+end_src
656 </guide | reference | org>
657 <org>
658 <*guide | reference>
659 \end{clibox} %$$
660 </guide | reference>
661 <*guide>
662 \begin{description}
663   \item[-s] Silent mode --- no progress output.
664   \item[-L] Follow redirects (often necessary for Zenodo).
665 \end{description}
666
667 Next step is to get the checksum of the downloaded file.
668 </guide>
669 <*guide | reference>
670 \begin{clibox}[org]{checksum of local file}
671 </guide | reference>
672 <org>** Get the checksum from local file
673 <*guide | reference | org>
674 #+name: file-checksum
675 #+begin_src shell
676 md5sum Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv | awk '{print $1}'
677 #+end_src
678 </guide | reference | org>
679 <org>

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680 (*guide | reference)
681 \end{clibox} %$$
682 </guide | reference>
683 (*guide)
684
685 \subsection{Demo 3 --- Verify Integrity (Checksum Match)}
686 Comparing the files is done using variables in the source block header.
687 The rest is plain \texttt{bash} code.
688 </guide>
689 (*guide | reference)
690 \begin{clibox}[org]{checksum comparison}
691 </guide | reference>
692 (org)** Verify Integrity (Checksum Match)
693 (*guide | reference | org)
694 #+name: compare-checksums
695 #+begin_src bash :var remote=curl-checksum :var local=file-checksum
696 [[ "$remote" == "$local" ]] && echo -n "MATCH: $local" || echo "MISMATCH"
697 #+end_src
698 </guide | reference | org>
699 (org)
700 (*guide | reference)
701 \end{clibox} %$$
702 </guide | reference>
703 (*guide)
704 \begin{keypointsbox}
705 \begin{itemize}
706 \item The remote checksum comes from the repository metadata; the local one is
707 computed from the downloaded file.
708 \item A matching checksum guarantees data integrity --- a key requirement of
709 Good Scientific Practice.
710 \item This pattern (fetch $\to$ download $\to$ verify) is the gold standard for
711 reproducible data acquisition.
712 \end{itemize}
713 \end{keypointsbox}
714 </guide>
715 (*guide | handout)
716 \begin{challengebox}{Explore the Zenodo API}
717 \begin{enumerate}
718 \item Query the full metadata record and pretty-print it:\\
719 \texttt{curl -sL "https://zenodo.org/api/records/15880071" | jq '.'}
720 \item Extract just the title and publication date:\\
721 \texttt{jq -r '.metadata.title, .metadata.publication\_date'}
722 \end{enumerate}
723 \bonus{Find out how many files are attached to this record:
724 pipe through \texttt{jq '.files | length'}}
725 \end{challengebox}
726 </guide | handout>
727 (*guide)
728 % -- sed -----
729 \section{sed (1974) --- 15 min}
730
731 \rdmphase{Production}
732
733 \medskip
734 \texttt{sed} is a stream editor for transforming text --- fast, scriptable, and
735 reliable even on very large files. It excels at data cleaning: normalising
736 metadata, harmonising formats, and fixing systematic errors.
737
738 Because transformations are declared in plain text, they are transparent,
739 auditable, and reproducible --- robust for FAIR-aligned workflows and
740 provenance tracking.
741
742 \begin{clibox}[org]{basic syntax}
743 #+begin_src bash :eval never

```

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744 sed [FLAGS] 's/pattern/replacement/g' [FILE]
745 #+end_src
746 \end{clibox}
747
748 \begin{description}
749   \item[s] Substitute: search for \textit{pattern}, write \textit{replacement}.
750   \item[g] Global flag --- replace \emph{all} matches per line.
751 \end{description}
752
753 \subsection{Demo 1 --- Fix a Misspelling In-Place with Backup}
754 </guide>
755 <*guide | reference>
756 \begin{clibox}[org]{clean data with backup}
757 </guide | reference>
758 <org>* sed (1974)
759 <org>** Fix a Misspelling In-Place with Backup
760 <*guide | reference | org>
761 #+name: sed-cleaning-delimiter
762 #+begin_src bash
763 sed -i.bak 's|NFDI-NFDI-MatWerk|NFDI-MatWerk|g' \
764   Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv \
765   && echo "file cleaned."
766 #+end_src
767 </guide | reference | org>
768 <org>
769 <*guide | reference>
770 \end{clibox}
771 </guide | reference>
772 <*guide>
773
774 \begin{description}
775   \item[-i] Edit the file in place (replaces the original).
776   \item[.bak] Creates \texttt{Collaboration\_of\_Consortia\_2025.csv.bak}.
777   \item[\textbar{}] Alternate delimiter --- avoids escaping slashes in paths.
778 \end{description}
779
780 \subsection{[Optional] Advanced: Regex with Capture Groups}
781
782 \begin{clibox}[bash]{swap two CSV fields}
783 sed -E 's/^(^,+), [[:space:]]*(^,+)$/\2, \1/' [FILE]
784 \end{clibox} %$$
785
786 \begin{description}
787   \item[^\{\}\ldots\}$] Anchors to the full line.
788   \item[({}\^{\},)+] One or more non-comma characters (capture group).
789   \item[\textbackslash{}2, \textbackslash{}1] Reinsert captured groups in reversed order.
790 \end{description}
791
792 \begin{tipsbox}
793 \begin{itemize}
794   \item Always use \texttt{-i.bak} (alternatively \texttt{-i.ws} works, too) rather than raw \texttt{-i}
795     in demos ---
796     it reinforces provenance habits.
797   \item The alternate delimiter (\texttt{|}) is a practical tip that participants will use immediately.
798   \item Verify right away: \texttt{ls Coll*} to show both files exist.
799 \end{itemize}
800 \end{tipsbox}
801 </guide>
802 <*guide | handout>
803 \begin{challengebox}{Normalise a Second Pattern}
804 \begin{enumerate}
805   \item Check whether \texttt{NFDI4Ing} appears with alternate capitalisation
806     using \texttt{grep -i}, then fix with \texttt{sed -i} if needed.
807   \item Use \texttt{sed -n} with the \texttt{p} flag to print \emph{only}

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807     changed lines --- without modifying the file.
808 \end{enumerate}
809 \bonus{Chain two substitutions in one command using \texttt{-e}:
810   \texttt{sed -e 's/A/B/' -e 's/C/D/'}}
811 \end{challengebox}
812 </guide | handout>
813 <*guide>
814 % -- grep -----
815 \section{grep (1973) --- 10 min}
816
817 \rdmphase{Production · Analysis}
818
819 \medskip
820 \texttt{grep} --- from the Unix \textit{ed} command \texttt{g/re/p}. Extremely
821 fast, works on arbitrarily large files, supports full regular expressions.
822
823 \subsubsection{RDM Use Cases}
824
825 \begin{itemize}
826   \item \textbf{Identifier validation} (DOIs, ORCIDs, grant IDs) and quick
827     conformance checks on headers or required fields.
828   \item \textbf{Quality gates} in pipelines --- detect missing/forbidden values
829     before publishing data.
830   \item \textbf{Provenance & auditing} --- save search rules and match counts
831     alongside datasets.
832   \item \textbf{Interoperability} in UNIX pipelines: combine with \texttt{sed},
833     \texttt{awk}, \texttt{sort}/\texttt{uniq} for reproducible, end-to-end checks.
834 \end{itemize}
835
836 \begin{clibox}[org]{basic syntax}
837 #+begin_src bash :eval never
838 grep [FLAGS] PATTERN [FILE ...]
839 #+end_src
840 \end{clibox}
841
842 \begin{description}
843   \item[-i] Ignore case.
844   \item[-v] Invert match --- show lines \emph{without} the pattern.
845   \item[-c] Count matching lines.
846   \item[-n] Show line numbers where matches occur.
847   \item[-r] Search recursively through directories.
848   \item[-E] Use extended regular expressions.
849 \end{description}
850
851 \subsection{Demo 1 --- Verify the sed Cleaning Worked}
852 </guide>
853 <*guide | reference>
854 \begin{clibox}[org]{verify cleaning}
855 </guide | reference>
856 <org>* grep (1973)
857 <org>** Verify the sed Cleaning Worked
858 <*guide | reference | org>
859 #+begin_src bash :results verbatim
860 grep -ci 'NFDI-NFDI-MatWerk' Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv \
861   || echo "file properly cleaned."
862 #+end_src
863 </guide | reference | org>
864 <org>
865 <*guide | reference>
866 \end{clibox}
867 </guide | reference>
868 <*guide>
869
870 You get either a number for existing instances of the search term or:

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871 Exit code \texttt{0} from \texttt{grep} means no matches.
872 We exploit this with \texttt{||} to print a confirmation.
873
874 \subsection{Demo 2 --- Filter Dataset with Complex Pattern}
875 Next we want to apply a regex pattern. We search for each line in which
876 \texttt{NFDI-MatWerk} is part of something that is \texttt{ongoing}.
877 Note: here limited to the first line (\verb/ | head -1 /).
878 </guide>
879 <*guide | reference>
880 \begin{clibox}[org]{complex pattern matching}
881 </guide | reference>
882 <org>** Filter Dataset with Complex Pattern
883 <*guide | reference | org>
884 #+begin_src bash :results verbatim
885 grep -E "^Event:(.+?)MatWerk(.+?);ongoing$" Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv | head -1
886 #+end_src
887 </guide | reference | org>
888 <org>
889 <*guide | reference>
890 \end{clibox} %$$
891 </guide | reference>
892 <*guide>
893
894 \begin{description}
895   \item[^\{}Event:] Line must start with \texttt{Event:}.
896   \item[(.+?)MatWerk] \texttt{MatWerk} must appear somewhere in the middle.
897   \item[;ongoing\$] Line must end with \texttt{;ongoing}.
898 \end{description}
899
900 \begin{keypointsbox}
901 \begin{itemize}
902   \item grep + regular expressions let you validate entire datasets in seconds,
903     even at gigabyte scale.
904   \item Combine with \texttt{-c} to get counts for reports, or redirect output to a
905     log file for auditing.
906   \item The same regex patterns used in grep can be used in sed and awk ---
907     consistency across tools.
908 \end{itemize}
909 \end{keypointsbox}
910 </guide>
911 <*guide | handout>
912 \begin{challengebox}{Validate and Count Your Own Consortium}
913 \begin{enumerate}
914   \item Pick any NFDI consortium (e.g.\ \texttt{NFDI4Chem}, \texttt{FAIRagro},
915     \texttt{Text+}).
916   \item Count how many lines mention it:\\
917     \texttt{grep -c 'YourConsortium' Collaboration\_of\_Consortia\_2025.csv}
918   \item List only lines where it appears \emph{and} the collaboration is
919     \texttt{ongoing}.
920   \item Save results to \texttt{results-YourConsortium/grep-summary.txt}
921     (create the folder first with \texttt{mkdir -p}).
922 \end{enumerate}
923 \hint
924 \begin{inlinecode}
925 grep -i 'NFDI4Chem' Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv | grep 'ongoing'
926 \end{inlinecode}
927 \end{challengebox}
928 </guide | handout>
929 <*guide>
930 % -- diff -----
931 \section{diff (1974) --- 10 min}
932 \rdmphase{Analysis}
933
934 \medskip

```

```

935 \texttt{diff} was designed to detect line-by-line differences between text files
936 --- an idea that evolved into all modern version control systems (RCS, CVS, Git).
937 For RDM it is the simplest yet most powerful verification tool.
938
939 \subsubsection{RDM Use Cases}
940
941 \begin{itemize}
942   \item Tracking and documenting changes in datasets, code, or metadata.
943   \item Validating reproducibility by comparing generated outputs against references.
944   \item Auditing transformations (e.g.\ after \texttt{sed} or \texttt{awk} processing).
945   \item Verifying integrity of archived or published files.
946 \end{itemize}
947
948 \begin{clibox}[org]{basic syntax}
949 \#+begin_src bash :eval never
950 diff [FLAGS] [FILE1] [FILE2]
951 \#+end_src
952 \end{clibox}
953
954 \begin{description}
955   \item[-u] Unified format --- 3 lines of context per change (most readable).
956   \item[-q] Brief --- only report if files differ.
957   \item[-y] Side-by-side comparison.
958   \item[-U\textit{n}] Unified format with \(\textit{n}\) lines of context.
959 \end{description}
960
961
962 \subsection{Demo --- Compare Original and Cleaned CSV}
963
964 </guide>
965 <*guide | reference>
966 \begin{clibox}[org]{compare files}
967 </guide | reference>
968 (org)* diff (1974)
969 <*guide | reference | org>
970 \#+name: diff-csv
971 \#+begin_src bash :results output
972 diff -u -U0 Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv.bak Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv | head -
973 5
974 \#+end_src
975 </guide | reference | org>
976 <org>
977 <*guide | reference>
978 \end{clibox}
979 </guide | reference>
980 <*guide>
981 Expected output:
982
983 \begin{clibox}[diff]{unified diff output}
984 --- Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv.bak 2025-10-21 15:51:58
985 +++ Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv 2025-10-21 15:52:24
986 @@ -11 +11 @@
987 -...NFDI-NFDI-MatWerk...
988 +...NFDI-MatWerk...
989 \end{clibox}
990
991 \begin{description}
992   \item[@@ -11 +11 @@] Line 11 in the old file was replaced by line 11 in the new.
993   \item[-] Lines removed from the old file.
994   \item[+] Lines added to the new file.
995 \end{description}
996
997 \begin{tipsbox}
998 \begin{itemize}

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998 \item Emphasise: this diff output \emph{is} the audit trail. It can be saved,
999     versioned, and attached to a data publication.
1000 \item diff is what makes Git possible --- every Git commit stores diffs under the hood.
1001 \end{itemize}
1002 \end{tipsbox}
1003 </guide>
1004
1005 (*guide | handout)
1006 \begin{challengebox}{Audit Your Own Transformation}
1007 \begin{enumerate}
1008 \item Open the CSV in Emacs (\verb|C-x C-f|), add a typo to line 5, save as
1009     \texttt{Collaboration\_modified.csv} (\verb|C-x C-w|).
1010 \item Run \texttt{diff -u Collaboration\_of\_Consortia\_2025.csv
1011     Collaboration\_modified.csv} and read the output.
1012 \item Try \texttt{diff -q} (brief) and \texttt{diff -y} (side-by-side).
1013 \item Save as a dated audit log:
1014     \texttt{diff -u ... > audit-\$(date +%Y%m%d).patch}
1015 \end{enumerate}
1016 \hint
1017 \begin{inlinecode}
1018 diff -u original.csv modified.csv > audit-\$(date +%Y%m%d).patch
1019 \end{inlinecode}
1020 \bonus{Re-apply the patch: \texttt{patch original.csv audit-20250319.patch}.
1021     Test first with \texttt{patch --dry-run ...}}
1022 \end{challengebox} %$$
1023 </guide | handout>
1024 (*guide)
1025 \begin{breakcard}
1026 {\large\bfseries\color{white} \ding{108}\enspace BREAK --- 10 minutes \ding{108}}
1027 \end{breakcard}
1028 % -- make -----
1029 \newpage
1030 \section{make (1976) --- 30 min}
1031
1032 \rdmphase{Production · Analysis · Archiving}
1033
1034 \medskip
1035 A \texttt{makefile} ties the entire workflow together: it evaluates all org-babel
1036 source blocks, writes results back into the \texttt{.org} file, and exports to
1037 one or more output formats --- all with a single command.
1038 This makes the analysis fully reproducible: anyone with Emacs and \texttt{make}
1039 can regenerate every result from scratch.
1040 </guide>
1041 (*guide | reference)
1042 \begin{clibox}[makefile]{makefile for the project}
1043 PROJECT = nfdi-analysis
1044 EMACS   ?= emacs
1045 ORGFILE := $(PROJECT).org
1046 SHELL   := bash
1047
1048 # -- Export formats -----
1049 EXPORTS += -f org-ascii-export-to-ascii # → .txt
1050 EXPORTS += -f org-md-export-to-markdown # → .md
1051 EXPORTS += -f org-html-export-to-html   # → .html
1052
1053 # -- Shared Emacs flags -----
1054 EMACS_FLAGS = -Q --batch
1055 EMACS_FLAGS += -l org -l ob -l ob-shell -l ob-awk -l ob-org
1056 EMACS_FLAGS += "$(ORGFILE)"
1057 EMACS_FLAGS += --eval "(setq org-confirm-babel-evaluate nil)"
1058
1059 .PHONY: all execute export clean
1060
1061 all: execute export

```

```

1062 @echo "* done *"
1063
1064 execute:
1065 @echo "* evaluating source blocks in $(ORGFIL) *"
1066 $(EMACS) $(EMACS_FLAGS) \
1067   --eval "(org-babel-execute-buffer)" \
1068   --eval "(save-buffer)"
1069 @echo "* source blocks evaluated *"
1070
1071 export:
1072 @echo "* exporting $(ORGFIL) *"
1073 $(EMACS) $(EMACS_FLAGS) \
1074   --eval "(setq org-export-use-babel nil)" \
1075   --eval "(setq org-html-htmlize-output-type nil)" \
1076   $(EXPORTS)
1077 @echo "* exported *"
1078
1079 clean:
1080 @rm -f $(PROJECT).txt $(PROJECT).md $(PROJECT).html
1081 @echo "* cleaned *"
1082 \end{clibox}
1083 </guide|reference>
1084 <*guide>
1085 \subsection{Variables}
1086
1087 \texttt{PROJECT} is the only value you ever need to change ---
1088 everything else derives from it.
1089
1090 \medskip
1091 \begin{description}
1092   \item[=] Recursive (lazy) assignment --- expanded each time the variable is used.
1093   \item[?] Conditional assignment --- only takes effect if the variable is \emph{not}
1094     already set in your environment.
1095     \texttt{EMACS ?= emacs} means you can override it without
1096     editing the file: \verb|make EMACS=/opt/homebrew/bin/emacs|
1097   \item[:=] Immediate assignment --- \texttt{\$(PROJECT)} is expanded right
1098     now at parse time and stored as a fixed string.
1099   \item[+=] Appends to the variable, so you can activate as many output
1100     formats as you want by simply uncommenting lines.
1101 \end{description}
1102
1103 \subsection{Export Formats}
1104
1105 Each value is a complete Emacs command-line fragment ---
1106 \texttt{-f} followed by an org export function name.
1107 All active formats are passed together to a single Emacs process and
1108 executed in sequence, producing all output files in one run.
1109
1110 \medskip
1111 \begin{description}
1112   \item[-f org-ascii-export-to-ascii] Plain text \texttt{.txt}
1113   \item[-f org-md-export-to-markdown] Markdown \texttt{.md}
1114   \item[-f org-html-export-to-html] HTML \texttt{.html}
1115   \item[-f org-latex-export-to-latex] \LaTeX{} \texttt{.tex}
1116 \end{description}
1117
1118 \subsection{Shared Emacs Flags --- DRY in Practice}
1119
1120 Both \texttt{execute} and \texttt{export} call Emacs with the same
1121 startup flags, the same libraries, the same file, and the same
1122 initial \texttt{--eval}.
1123 Rather than writing them out twice, \texttt{EMACS\_FLAGS} collects
1124 everything shared into one variable.
1125 Each target then only appends its own specific \texttt{--eval} calls.

```

```

1126
1127 This is the DRY principle --- \emph{Don't Repeat Yourself} --- applied to
1128 a Makefile: adding a new library or changing the org filename now requires
1129 editing exactly one place.
1130
1131 \medskip
1132 \begin{description}
1133   \item[-Q] \textbf{Quick start} --- skip loading the user's personal init file
1134     (\texttt{\textasciitilde/.emacs} or \texttt{\textasciitilde/.emacs.d/init.el}),
1135     all site-start files, and all default customisations.
1136     This guarantees reproducible results on any machine,
1137     regardless of what packages or settings a particular user has installed.
1138     Without \texttt{-Q}, a source block might run on your laptop but fail
1139     silently on a colleague's because of a different Emacs configuration.
1140   \item[--batch] Run non-interactively and exit when done.
1141     No windows, no prompts, no GUI --- output goes to the terminal.
1142   \item[-l org] Load the org-mode library.
1143   \item[-l ob] Load the org-babel dispatcher.
1144   \item[-l ob-shell -l ob-awk -l ob-org] Load the language backends explicitly.
1145     In batch mode Emacs does not auto-load these, so without them it would
1146     not know how to execute \texttt{bash}, \texttt{awk}, or \texttt{org}
1147     source blocks.
1148   \item["\$(ORGFILe)"] Pass the file as a positional argument.
1149     Emacs opens it as the current buffer, which is what
1150     \texttt{org-babel-execute-buffer} and the \texttt{-f} export functions
1151     implicitly act on.
1152   \item[--eval "\ldots{}nil"] Disable the interactive confirmation prompt that
1153     org-babel shows before running code --- essential in batch mode since
1154     there is nobody to click yes.
1155 \end{description}
1156
1157 \subsection{\texttt{execute} --- Evaluate the Source Blocks}
1158
1159 \texttt{\$(EMACS\_FLAGS)} expands to the full shared flag list.
1160 Two additional \texttt{--eval} calls follow:
1161
1162 \medskip
1163 \begin{description}
1164   \item[(org-babel-execute-buffer)] Run every source block in the file in sequence.
1165     Results are written into \texttt{\#+RESULTS:} blocks inline.
1166   \item[(save-buffer)] Write the updated buffer back to disk, so the \texttt{export}
1167     step that follows reads fresh results.
1168 \end{description}
1169
1170 \subsection{\texttt{export} --- Produce the Output Files}
1171
1172 \texttt{\$(EMACS\_FLAGS)} provides the shared base.
1173 Three additions follow:
1174
1175 \medskip
1176 \begin{description}
1177   \item[org-export-use-babel nil] Prevents org from re-executing source blocks
1178     during export. The results are already in the file from the \texttt{execute}
1179     step --- no need to run everything twice.
1180   \item[org-html-htmlize-output-type nil] Suppresses warnings about missing
1181     \texttt{htmlize.el}. Without this, the HTML backend emits a warning for every
1182     code block when the library is not available in the bare \texttt{-Q} session.
1183   \item["\$(EXPORTS)"] Expands to all active \texttt{-f~\ldots} fragments ---
1184     one Emacs process, all output formats.
1185 \end{description}
1186
1187 \subsection{\texttt{clean} --- Remove Generated Files}
1188
1189 Removes all generated output files.

```

```

1190 The source \texttt{.org} file and any downloaded data are left untouched.
1191
1192 \subsection{\texttt{.PHONY}}
1193
1194 \texttt{.PHONY} tells \texttt{make} that these target names are not real
1195 files on disk.
1196 Without it, if a file called \texttt{clean} happened to exist in the
1197 directory, \texttt{make clean} would see it, conclude the target is already
1198 up to date, and do nothing --- silently skipping the deletion.
1199
1200 \begin{keypointsbox}
1201 \begin{itemize}
1202   \item \texttt{-Q} is the key to reproducibility: stripping personal
1203     configuration means the result is identical on every machine.
1204   \item \texttt{EMACS\_FLAGS} is the DRY principle in action ---
1205     shared setup lives in one place; each target only adds what it
1206     specifically needs.
1207   \item \texttt{execute} runs before \texttt{export}: the
1208     \texttt{\#+RESULTS:} blocks are always fresh when the document is
1209     exported.
1210   \item Activating multiple export formats costs nothing extra ---
1211     one Emacs process, one run, all files.
1212 \end{itemize}
1213 \end{keypointsbox}
1214
1215 \begin{tipsbox}
1216 \begin{itemize}
1217   \item Use \texttt{-Q} as the entry point for explaining reproducibility:
1218     \emph{``Would this run the same way on your colleague's laptop?''}
1219     That question frames the whole argument for batch and no-config execution.
1220   \item The \texttt{EMACS\_FLAGS} refactoring is a good live coding moment ---
1221     show the before (duplicated flags in both targets) and the after
1222     (shared variable) side by side so participants immediately see the value.
1223   \item If a source block fails silently in batch mode, the first debugging
1224     step is always to run it interactively in Emacs first (\texttt{C-c C-c})
1225     and only then call \texttt{make execute}.
1226 \end{itemize}
1227 \end{tipsbox}
1228 </guide>
1229 <*guide | handout>
1230 \begin{challengebox}{Extend the Makefile}
1231 \begin{enumerate}
1232   \item Activate the Markdown export by uncommenting the relevant \texttt{EXPORTS}
1233     line and run \texttt{make} --- confirm \texttt{nfdi-analysis.md} is created.
1234   \item Add a \texttt{test} target that runs only \texttt{execute} (no export).
1235   \item Run \texttt{make -n} to do a dry-run and observe which commands
1236     \emph{would} execute without running them.
1237   \item What happens when you remove \texttt{-Q} from \texttt{EMACS\_FLAGS}?
1238 \end{enumerate}
1239 \bonus{Add a \texttt{help} target that prints each available target and a one-line
1240   description using \texttt{@echo}.}
1241 \end{challengebox}
1242 </guide | handout>
1243 <*guide>
1244 % -- awk -----
1245 \section{awk (1977) --- 40 min}
1246
1247 \rdmphase{Analysis · Production}
1248
1249 \medskip
1250 \texttt{awk} (named after its creators: Aho, Weinberger, Kernighan) combines a
1251 streaming text processor, a pattern matcher, and a lightweight programming
1252 language. It handles column-based datasets like CSV directly --- bridging
1253 grep/sed filtering and high-level statistical scripting.

```

```

1254
1255 \subsubsection{What awk can do that sed/grep cannot}
1256
1257 \begin{itemize}
1258   \item Perform real-time calculations and aggregations.
1259   \item Handle column-based datasets natively (no pre-parsing needed).
1260   \item Extract, transform, and summarise data in one pass.
1261   \item Produce structured output for further analysis or reporting.
1262 \end{itemize}
1263
1264 \begin{clibox}[awk]{general awk structure}
1265 awk -F',' 'BEGIN { init } pattern { action } END { summary }' [FILE]
1266 \end{clibox}
1267
1268 \begin{description}
1269   \item[-F',' ] Field separator (here \texttt{,} for CSV; use \texttt{;} for
1270     semicolon-separated files).
1271   \item[ $\$1, \$2$ ] Columns/fields; \texttt{NF} = number of fields;
1272     \texttt{NR} = current record number.
1273   \item[BEGIN] Initialisation block: runs once before input.
1274   \item[pattern] Condition or regex tested per line: e.g. \texttt{\$3 > 0}
1275     or \texttt{/MatWerk/}.
1276   \item[action] Command run when pattern matches.
1277   \item[END] Finalisation block: runs once after all lines.
1278 \end{description}
1279
1280 \subsection{Demo 1 --- Inline Aggregation}
1281
1282 Running awk directly in an org-babel source block keeps code, input, and
1283 results in the same \texttt{.org} file.
1284
1285 </guide>
1286 <*guide | reference>
1287 \begin{clibox}[org]{count collaboration types (bash block)}
1288 </guide | reference>
1289 <org>* awk (1977)
1290 <org>** Inline Aggregation
1291 <*guide | reference | org>
1292 #+name: awk-with-bash
1293 #+begin_src bash :results verbatim
1294 awk -F',' ' /NFDI-MatWerk/ {cnt[$1]++; total++}
1295   END{
1296     print "---- NFDI-MatWerk ----"
1297     for(t in cnt) print t, cnt[t]
1298     print "TOTAL:", total}' Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv
1299 #+end_src
1300 </guide | reference | org>
1301 <org>
1302 <*guide | reference>
1303 \end{clibox}%%$
1304 </guide | reference>
1305 <*guide>
1306
1307 \subsection{Demo 2 --- Full Script (\texttt{affiliation-count-by-type})}
1308 Now we switch from a \texttt{bash}-source block to an \texttt{awk}-source block directly.
1309
1310 The header arguments tell org-babel where the data comes from, what variables
1311 to pass in, and how to format the output.
1312 </guide>
1313 <*guide | reference>
1314 \begin{clibox}[org]{awk source block}
1315 </guide | reference>
1316 <org>** awk Source Block with Header Arguments
1317 <*guide | reference | org>

```

```

1318 #+name: affiliation-count-by-type
1319 #+begin_src awk :in-file Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv :var consortium="NFDI-MatWerk" :results v
1320 BEGIN { FS = ";" }
1321 $0 ~ consortium { cnt[$1]++; total++ }
1322 END {
1323   print "---- " consortium " ----"
1324   for (t in cnt) print t, cnt[t]
1325   print "TOTAL:", total
1326 }
1327 #+end_src
1328 </guide | reference | org>
1329 <org>
1330 <*guide | reference>
1331 \end{clibox}
1332 </guide | reference>
1333 <*guide>
1334 \begin{description}
1335   \item[:in-file] Pass a file directly to the awk process as standard input ---
1336     equivalent to writing the filename at the end of an awk command in the shell.
1337     The file path is relative to the \texttt{.org} file's directory.
1338   \item[:var] Declare a named variable and its default value.
1339     Inside the awk code the variable is available by name (here: \texttt{consortium}).
1340     The value can be overridden when calling the block with \verb|#+call:| without
1341     editing the source block itself.
1342   \item[:results] Control how org-babel formats the output.
1343     \texttt{verbatim} inserts the raw text output as-is inside a \verb|#+RESULTS:|
1344     block, preserving spacing and alignment.
1345     The alternative \texttt{table} would parse the output as an org table.
1346 \end{description}
1347
1348 \medskip
1349 The variable passed via \texttt{:var} is injected by org-babel as an awk
1350 \texttt{-v} flag at runtime.
1351 The block above therefore executes as:
1352
1353 \begin{clibox}[bash]{what org-babel runs under the hood}
1354 awk -v consortium="NFDI-MatWerk" '
1355 BEGIN { FS = ";" }
1356 $0 ~ consortium { cnt[$1]++; total++ }
1357 END {
1358   print "---- " consortium " ----"
1359   for (t in cnt) print t, cnt[t]
1360   print "TOTAL:", total
1361 }' Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv
1362 \end{clibox}
1363
1364 \subsubsection{Line by line}
1365
1366 \begin{description}
1367   \item[BEGIN \{ FS = ";" \}] Runs once before reading any input.
1368     \texttt{FS} is awk's built-in \emph{field separator} variable.
1369     Setting it to \texttt{";"} tells awk to split each line on semicolons,
1370     so \texttt{\$1}, \texttt{\$2}, \ldots{} refer to the individual columns
1371     of the semicolon-delimited CSV.
1372   \item[\$0 \textasciitilde{} consortium] The pattern tested on every line.
1373     \texttt{\$0} is awk's built-in variable for the \emph{entire current line}.
1374     \texttt{\textasciitilde{}} is the regex-match operator --- the action block
1375     only executes when the line matches \texttt{consortium}.
1376   \item[cnt[{}\$1{}]++] \texttt{cnt} is a user-defined \emph{associative array}
1377     (key--value store). \texttt{\$1} is the value of the \emph{first column}
1378     (the collaboration type, e.g. \texttt{Event: workshop}).
1379     \texttt{++} increments the counter for that key by one.
1380     If the key does not exist yet, awk initialises it to zero automatically ---
1381     no explicit initialisation needed.

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1382 \item[total++] A plain numeric variable that counts every matching line,
1383     regardless of collaboration type.
1384     Like \texttt{cnt}, it starts at zero automatically on first use.
1385 \item[for (t in cnt)] Iterates over every key in the \texttt{cnt} array.
1386     \texttt{t} takes each key in turn (order is not guaranteed in awk).
1387     \texttt{print t, cnt[t]} outputs the type name and its count.
1388 \end{description}
1389
1390 \subsubsection{Data flow}
1391
1392 The three-block structure maps directly onto the research pipeline:
1393 \texttt{BEGIN} configures the tool, the pattern--action rule accumulates data
1394 line by line (never loading the whole file into memory), and \texttt{END}
1395 produces the summary report.
1396 Because awk processes the file in a single pass, this works efficiently even
1397 on large datasets.
1398
1399 \begin{keypointsbox}
1400 \begin{itemize}
1401   \item \texttt{FS} and \texttt{\$0}, \texttt{\$1}, \texttt{\$2} \ldots are
1402     \emph{built-in} awk variables --- they exist automatically.
1403   \item \texttt{cnt} and \texttt{total} are \emph{user-defined} --- awk
1404     creates them on first use, initialised to zero or empty string depending
1405     on context.
1406   \item Associative arrays (\texttt{cnt[\$1]}) let you group and count by any
1407     column value in a single pass, with no \texttt{sort} or pre-processing
1408     step.
1409   \item Replacing \texttt{\$1} with \texttt{\$2}, \texttt{\$3} etc.\ changes
1410     which column is used as the grouping key --- no other code change needed.
1411 \end{itemize}
1412 \end{keypointsbox}
1413
1414 \subsection{Demo 3 --- Reuse the Block}
1415
1416 Using \texttt{\$0 \textasciitilde{} consortium} instead of a hard-coded regex
1417 \texttt{/NFDI-MatWerk/} is essential: a literal regex is fixed at parse time
1418 and ignores the \texttt{:var} value entirely, whereas \texttt{\$0 \textasciitilde{} consortium}
1419 tests against the variable at runtime.
1420 This means swapping the consortium requires no code change --- only the
1421 \texttt{:var} value:
1422 
1423 *guide | reference
1424 \begin{clibox}[org]{reuse for a different consortium}
1425 *guide | reference
1426 (org)** Reuse the Block
1427 *guide | reference | org
1428 #+call: affiliation-count-by-type (consortium="NFDI4ING")
1429 *guide | reference | org
1430 (org)
1431 *guide | reference
1432 \end{clibox}
1433 *guide | reference
1434 *guide

1435 \subsection{Demo 4 --- Write Results to a File}
1436
1437 So far every block has written its output into the buffer as \texttt{\#+RESULTS:}.
1438 For archiving and reproducibility it is often better to write results directly
1439 to a file on disk --- for example to collect them later with \texttt{tar} or
1440 deposit them in a repository.
1441 Org-babel handles this entirely through header arguments: no shell
1442 redirection, no \texttt{tee}, no changes to the awk code itself.
1443 
1444 *guide | reference
1445 \begin{clibox}[org]{write result to file}


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```

1446 </guide | reference>
1447 <org>** Write Results to a File
1448 <*guide | reference | org>
1449 #+name: affiliation-count-to-file
1450 #+begin_src awk :in-file ../Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv :var consortium="NFDI4Chem" :results fi
NFDI4Chem :mkdirp yes :file analysis-overview.txt
1451 BEGIN { FS = ";" }
1452 $0 ~ consortium { cnt[$1]++; total++ }
1453 END {
1454   print "---- " consortium " ----"
1455   for (t in cnt) print t, cnt[t]
1456   print "TOTAL:", total
1457 }
1458 #+end_src
1459 </guide | reference | org>
1460 <org>
1461 <*guide | reference>
1462 \end{clibox}
1463 </guide | reference>
1464 <*guide>
1465
1466 Four header arguments work together here:
1467
1468 \medskip
1469 \begin{description}
1470   \item[:results file] Instead of inserting the output into the buffer, org-babel
1471     captures stdout and writes it to a file.
1472     The \texttt{\#+RESULTS:} block becomes a link to that file rather than
1473     the content itself.
1474   \item[:dir results-NFDI4Chem] Sets the working directory for the block.
1475     Both the \texttt{:file} path and the \texttt{:in-file} path are resolved
1476     relative to this directory --- which is why \texttt{:in-file} needs the
1477     \texttt{../} prefix to reach the CSV one level up.
1478   \item[:mkdirp yes] Creates the \texttt{:dir} directory if it does not exist yet.
1479     This is what \texttt{mkdir -p} would do in a shell block.
1480   \item[:file analysis-overview.txt] The filename org-babel writes to inside the
1481     \texttt{:dir} directory.
1482     The resulting full path is \texttt{results-NFDI4Chem/analysis-overview.txt}.
1483 \end{description}
1484
1485 \medskip
1486 To run the same analysis for a different consortium, use \texttt{\#+call:}
1487 and override \texttt{:dir} and the \texttt{consortium} variable at the call
1488 site --- the block definition stays untouched:
1489
1490 </guide>
1491 <*guide | reference>
1492 \begin{clibox}[org]{reuse write-to-file for a different consortium}
1493 </guide | reference>
1494 <org>
1495 <*guide | reference | org>
1496 #+call: affiliation-count-to-file[:dir results-NFDI4ING] (consortium="NFDI4ING")
1497 </guide | reference | org>
1498 <org>
1499 <*guide | reference>
1500 \end{clibox}
1501 </guide | reference>
1502 <*guide>
1503
1504 Note that \texttt{:dir} and \texttt{:file} cannot reference \texttt{:var}
1505 values --- header arguments are not expanded against each other in org-babel.
1506 The consortium name therefore appears twice in the \texttt{\#+call:} line:
1507 once for the directory path and once as the variable value passed to awk.
1508 This is a known limitation; the workaround is a bash wrapper block that uses

```

```

1509 \texttt{tee} if having the name in one place matters.
1510
1511 \begin{tipsbox}
1512 \begin{itemize}
1513   \item The \texttt{\#+RESULTS:} link is clickable in Emacs --- press
1514     \texttt{C-c C-o} on it to open the file directly in a buffer.
1515   \item After collecting results for several consortia, the
1516     \texttt{results-*/} folders can be bundled in one step with \texttt{tar}
1517     (see the tar section) and the whole archive deposited in Zenodo.
1518   \item Show participants the folder structure with
1519     \mintinline{bash}{ls results-*/} after running a few \texttt{\#+call:}
1520     lines --- seeing the files appear on disk makes the workflow tangible.
1521   \item Instead of a named source-block you can also do a script file approach
1522     (\texttt{awk -f}), which is better than long inline awk for anything
1523     beyond 5 lines --- easier to version-control.
1524   \item Frame awk as the bridge between grep/sed and R/Python:
1525     \textit{``before you reach for pandas, try awk''}.
1526 \end{itemize}
1527 \end{tipsbox}
1528 \
1529 (*guide | handout)
1530 \begin{challengebox}{Aggregate Your Own Consortium}
1531 \begin{enumerate}
1532   \item Run \texttt{affiliation-count-by-type} for \texttt{NFDI4Chem} by changing
1533     only the \texttt{-v} value:
1534   \begin{inlinecode}[bash]
1535   awk -f affiliation-count-by-type \
1536     -v consortium=NFDI4Chem \
1537     Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv
1538   \end{inlinecode}
1539   \item How many distinct collaboration types exist in the whole file?
1540     Use the hint one-liner and count the output lines.
1541   \item Which consortium appears most often as Affiliated Lead/Chair (column 3)?
1542     Modify the one-liner to group by \texttt{\$3} instead of \texttt{\$1}, then
1543     pipe through \texttt{sort -t' ' -k2 -rn | head -5}.
1544 \end{enumerate}
1545 \hint
1546 \begin{inlinecode}[bash]
1547   awk -F';' '{cnt[$1]++} END{for(t in cnt) print t, cnt[t]}' \
1548     Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv
1549 \end{inlinecode}
1550 \bonus{Filter by both consortium and status: add \texttt{:var status="ongoing"}
1551   to the header and change the pattern to
1552   \texttt{\$0 \textasciitilde{} consortium \&\& \$0 \textasciitilde{} status}.}
1553 \end{challengebox}%%$
1554 \

```

```

1573 \item Transparent integration in automated workflows or HPC pipelines.
1574 \item Future-proof: every UNIX-like system will unpack a \texttt{.tar.gz}
1575     even decades later.
1576 \end{itemize}
1577
1578 Once all results are in place, bundle everything into a single
1579 \texttt{.tar.gz} and immediately compute a SHA-256 checksum.
1580 The \texttt{tee} command writes the checksum both to a file and to the
1581 terminal so you can confirm it at a glance.
1582
1583 \begin{description}
1584   \item[-c]   Create a new archive.
1585   \item[-z]   Compress with gzip (\texttt{.tar.gz}).
1586   \item[-f]   Write to the specified file.
1587   \item[--list] List archive contents without extracting.
1588 \end{description}
1589
1590 \subsection{Demo 1 --- Archive and Checksum the Pipeline Result}
1591 \</guide>
1592 \< *guide | reference>
1593 \begin{clibox}[org]{create archive with checksum}
1594 \</guide | reference>
1595 \< org>* tar (1979)
1596 \< org>** Archive and Checksum the Pipeline Result
1597 \< *guide | reference | org>
1598 \#+name: archive-files
1599 \#+begin_src bash :results verbatim
1600 tar -czf NFDI-results.tar.gz \
1601     makefile *.org \
1602     Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv \
1603     Collaboration_of_Consortia_2025.csv.bak \
1604     results-* / \
1605     && echo "file tape-archived."
1606 sha256sum NFDI-results.tar.gz | tee NFDI-results.tar.gz.sha256
1607 \#+end_src
1608 \</guide | reference | org>
1609 \< org>
1610 \< *guide | reference>
1611 \end{clibox}
1612 \</guide | reference>
1613 \< *guide>
1614 \subsection{Demo 2 --- List the archived files}
1615 After archiving, always verify the contents without unpacking.
1616 \texttt{tar --list} reads only the archive header --- it is instantaneous
1617 even for large archives and confirms that every expected file is present
1618 before the archive leaves your machine.
1619
1620 \</guide>
1621 \< *guide | reference>
1622 \begin{clibox}[org]{list archive}
1623 \</guide | reference>
1624 \< org>** List the archived files
1625 \< *guide | reference | org>
1626 \#+name: list-archive-files
1627 \#+begin_src bash
1628 tar --list -f NFDI-results.tar.gz | sort
1629 \#+end_src
1630 \</guide | reference | org>
1631 \< org>
1632 \< *guide | reference>
1633 \end{clibox}
1634 \</guide | reference>
1635 \< *guide>
1636

```

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1637 The sorted listing groups files alphabetically so you can immediately spot
1638 whether the cleaned CSV, the \texttt{.bak} provenance file, the workflow
1639 files, and all result folders are present.
1640 Anyone receiving this single \texttt{.tar.gz} can re-run the entire pipeline
1641 from scratch --- the archive is a complete, self-contained research object.
1642
1643 \begin{keypointsbox}
1644 \begin{itemize}
1645   \item The \texttt{.sha256} file accompanies the archive everywhere it goes.
1646   \item The archive contains both the cleaned CSV \emph{and} the \texttt{.bak}
1647     provenance file --- a complete, self-contained research object.
1648   \item This \texttt{.tar.gz} can be deposited in Zenodo with guaranteed integrity.
1649 \end{itemize}
1650 \end{keypointsbox}
1651 </guide>
1652 (*guide | handout)
1653 \begin{challengebox}{Archive and Verify Your Results}
1654 \begin{enumerate}
1655   \item Create a \texttt{.tar.gz} archive:\\
1656     \texttt{tar -czf my-results.tar.gz results-YourConsortium/}
1657   \item Generate a SHA-256 checksum:\\
1658     \texttt{sha256sum my-results.tar.gz | tee my-results.tar.gz.sha256}
1659   \item List the archive contents:\\
1660     \texttt{tar --list -f my-results.tar.gz}
1661   \item Extract into a new folder to verify:\\
1662     \texttt{mkdir verify/ \&\& tar -xzf my-results.tar.gz -C verify/}
1663   \item Compare the checksum of the re-extracted CSV with the original.
1664 \end{enumerate}
1665 \bonus{Use \texttt{tar --exclude='*.bak'} to create a clean archive omitting
1666   backup files --- useful when preparing a dataset for public deposit.}
1667 \bonus{Use \texttt{diff} from earlier to compare the files.}
1668 \end{challengebox}
1669 </guide | handout>
1670 (*guide)
1671 % -- Wrap-Up -----
1672 \section{Wrap-Up: the ROOT Concept \& Q\&A --- 10 min}
1673
1674 \subsection{The ROOT Badge}
1675
1676 Introduce ROOT as a conceptual badge applicable to all tools covered today:
1677
1678 \bigskip
1679 \begin{center}
1680 \begin{tabular}{@{}p{1.4cm}p{\dimexpr\linewidth-1.4cm-2\tabcolsep}@{}}
1681 \toprule
1682 \textbf{\large R} & \textbf{Robust} --- Works reliably on huge files, across
1683   platforms, without breaking. \\\[4pt]
1684 \textbf{\large O} & \textbf{Open} --- Free and open-source; no vendor lock-in;
1685   community-maintained. \\\[4pt]
1686 \textbf{\large O} & \textbf{Ongoing} --- Actively maintained; not a relic ---
1687   a living tool. \\\[4pt]
1688 \textbf{\large T} & \textbf{Time-tested} --- Proven over decades in real research
1689   environments. \\\
1690 \bottomrule
1691 \end{tabular}
1692 \end{center}
1693
1694 \subsection{Also Worth Mentioning (Bonus Tools)}
1695
1696 \begin{description}[leftmargin=2.8cm,labelwidth=2.5cm,font=\ttfamily\bfseries]
1697   \item[find (1974)] Recursively searches directory structures. Essential for
1698     navigating large research repositories.
1699   \item[LaTeX (1984)] The enduring standard for scientific writing --- DMPs,
1700     reports, posters, publications.

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1701  \item[perl (1987)] Versatile scripting for text manipulation, pattern
1702                recognition, metadata transformation.
1703  \item[rsync (1996)] Synchronises and mirrors directories efficiently.
1704                Transfers only differences.
1705  \item[SQLite (2000)] Serverless SQL in a single file. Excellent for metadata
1706                catalogs and portable archives.
1707  \end{description}
1708
1709  \subsection{Closing Discussion Questions}
1710
1711  \begin{itemize}
1712    \item Which of today's tools did you already know? Which surprised you?
1713    \item Where could \texttt{curl} + checksum verification replace a manual download?
1714    \item How would you add a \texttt{make} target to your next project?
1715    \item What would a ``resilient'' version of your own toolchain look like?
1716  \end{itemize}
1717
1718  \begin{tipsbox}
1719  \begin{itemize}
1720    \item Return to the poster wheel diagram: ask participants which phases each
1721          tool covers --- this cements the big picture.
1722    \item Mention that the entire poster was generated from an \texttt{.org} file.
1723          Similar to what they've seen today --- a living example of the concept.
1724    \item Leave 5 minutes for questions about the NFDI dataset itself ---
1725          participants may have domain-specific follow-ups.
1726    \item Share the Zenodo DOI \restDOIlink{} so participants can explore at home.
1727  \end{itemize}
1728  \end{tipsbox}
1729  </guide>
1730  <*guide | handout>
1731  \newpage
1732  \section*{Quick Reference --- All Demo Commands}
1733  \addcontentsline{toc}{section}{Quick Reference}
1734  \input{resilient-technologies-reference}
1735  \end{document}
1736  </guide | handout>

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